

Non-local Triggering in Rock Fracture

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Contents of open data in the folder

Beta=60Location&Magnitude.mat % containing the data for 60-degree test

Beta=70Location&Magnitude.mat % containing the data for 70-degree test

Variables in each of the .mat files

Location⁺: It is a 4-column matrix. The 1st to 3rd columns are the source location coordinates (in mm), and the 4th column is the source onset time (μ s). The origin point of the source location coordinate ($x = 0, y = 0, z = 0$) is the left-bottom (in x-y plane) point of the front surface (in z axis) in the specimen.

Log2by3M: A one-column array for the relative moment magnitude of the sources.

Preflaw: Its 1st to 4th elements are for the two x and two y coordinates of the central pre-flaw.

+: Only the sources after 1000s of testing time have been included, as two faster loading stages have completed in the first 550s. These stages have not initiated the rock fractures according to the AE, optical, and stress interpretations.

Other Explanations

- The mechanical loading information, including axial force and displacement versus time, has been shared in the support document of Wong and Xiong (2018).
- The key information from the optical observation has been presented in the manuscript as well as the reference (Wong and Xiong, 2018).
- Due to the limitation of storage space, the original video (~4.5 G), high-speed image (~ 30 G), and AE waveform data (size depends on the format) have not been uploaded. Please contact the author for the raw data.

Reference

Wong, L.N.Y., Xiong, Q., 2018. A Method for Multiscale Interpretation of Fracture Processes in Carrara Marble Specimen Containing a Single Flaw Under Uniaxial Compression. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*.